

Complexes of *p-p'*-bis(benzoyl thiourea)Benzene with Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) Salts and Their Biological Activity

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Metal complexes of the type, $[M(\text{BBTuB})X_2]$ [where $M = \text{Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II)}$; $\text{BBTuB} = p-p'$ -bis(benzoyl thiourea)benzene and $X = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{NO}_3^-, \text{ClO}_4^-$] have been prepared and characterized on the basis of IR spectra, electronic spectra and magnetic susceptibility measurements. Infrared spectra manifest the coordination of the ligand to the metal ion through carbonyl oxygen and thiocarbonyl sulphur atoms. The complexes possess octahedral stereochemistry as inferred from electronic spectral data and magnetic moment values. Fungicidal screening of the complexes shows them to be antifungal against *A. niger*, *F. oxysporium* and *H. oryzae*.

As a part of our investigations on the synthesis and structure elucidation of metal complexes of sulphur donor ligands¹⁻⁷, we report in the present communication the preparation and characterization of some metal complexes with *p-p'*-bis(benzoyl thiourea) benzene along with their fungicidal activity.

Experimental

The ligand, *p-p'*-bis(benzoyl thiourea)benzene was synthesized by reacting *p*-phenylene diamine, benzoyl chloride and ammonium thiocyanate in acetone medium⁸. It was recrystallized from DMF-alcohol mixture.

A DMF solution of the ligand was treated with an alcoholic solution of the appropriate metal(II) salt in the molar ratio 1 : 1 and the mixture was refluxed for 3-4 hr. The refluxed solution was reduced in volume and cooled when solids separated out which were filtered, washed with DMF-alcohol mixture and analysed after drying in vacuum.

The complexes are highly insoluble in water but sparingly soluble in dioxane and DMF. All the complexes decompose above 250°. Metal, sulphur and nitrogen content of the complexes were determined by Vogel's methods⁹. The analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

IR spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded on a Perkin Elmer model 221 Spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured by Gouy method using Mercury(II) tetrathiocyanato cobaltate(II) as the standard. Dimagnetic corrections were made using standard values¹⁰. Electronic spectra of the ligand and the metal complexes were recorded in dioxane.

Results and Discussion

The infrared spectrum of the ligand shows a strong and broad band in the region 3240-2990 cm^{-1}

corresponding to ν_{NH} vibrations being overlapped with the ν_{CH} vibrations of the phenyl group. This band remains almost unaffected in the metal complexes indicating the non-involvement of NH group in bond formation. Another strong band appears at $\sim 1660 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligand and may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ vibrations. This undergoes a shift to lower frequency region in the metal complexes and appears at $\sim 1640 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The shift suggests the coordination of carbonyl group to the metal ion.

A strong and broad band is observed in the frequency region 1600-1400 cm^{-1} of the ligand as well as in the metal complexes which most probably arises due to phenyl ring vibrations. Phenyl groups usually show four vibrational bands in this region which are of weak to medium in intensity. Another band of considerable intensity appears at 1150 cm^{-1} . We assign this band to $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ vibrations. Besides, a medium band is also observed at 705 cm^{-1} which is susceptible to coordination and arises due to $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ vibrations. As reported earlier¹¹, coordination of metal through sulphur leads to a decrease in $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ frequency and an increase in $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ frequency. In the metal complexes the C-N band undergoes a positive shift and appears at $\sim 1170 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. On the other hand the C=S band lowers by 25-30 cm^{-1} in the metal complexes which clearly implies the coordination of sulphur atom to the metal ion.

There are two to three bands observed in the spectra of the ligand in the region 700-650 cm^{-1} . These bands shift in an irregular way in the metal complexes.

Coordination of NO_3^- group¹² to the metal ion is evident by the presence of a medium band near about 1010 cm^{-1} . In the perchlorate complex we get three additional bands at $\sim 1250(\text{w})$, 1140(s) and 990(w) cm^{-1} which can be attributed to ν_s , ν_a and ν_1 vibrations¹³ respectively.

All the complexes are paramagnetic (Table 1). Electronic spectra of Cu(II) complexes show a

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF *p,p'*-bis(BENZOYL THIOUREA)BENZENE (BBTuB) AND ITS METAL COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour	μ_{eff} in B.M. ($29^\circ \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$)	Found(Calcd.)%		
			Metal	Sulphur	Nitrogen
BBTuB	Grey			14.65 (14.72)	12.55 (12.90)
[Cu(BBTuB)Cl ₂]	Dirty green	1.72	10.88 (11.17)	11.02 (11.25)	9.78 (9.85)
[Cu(BBTuB)Br ₂]	Leaf green	1.715	9.62 (9.66)	9.65 (9.73)	8.39 (8.51)
[Cu(BBTuB)(NO ₃) ₂]	Brown	1.72	10.12 (10.22)	10.01 (10.29)	9.00 (9.01)
[Cu(BBTuB)(ClO ₄) ₂]	Light green	1.72	8.94 (9.12)	9.00 (9.18)	7.98 (8.04)
[Co(BBTuB)Cl ₂]	Grey	4.61	10.08 (10.46)	11.09 (11.34)	9.39 (9.57)
[Co(BBTuB)Br ₂]	Grey	4.53	8.31 (9.02)	9.65 (9.80)	8.36 (8.57)
[Co(BBTuB)(NO ₃) ₂]	Green	4.62	8.45 (9.55)	10.26 (10.37)	8.79 (9.07)
[Co(BBTuB)(ClO ₄) ₂]	A. C. grey	4.55	8.02 (8.51)	9.11 (9.27)	7.90 (8.09)
[Ni(BBTuB)Cl ₂]	New olive green	2.60	9.86 (10.41)	11.02 (11.35)	9.12 (9.57)
[Ni(BBTuB)Br ₂]	New s. c. grey	2.64	8.52 (8.99)	9.51 (9.80)	8.09 (8.57)
[Ni(BBTuB)(NO ₃) ₂]	Pale rose	2.62	8.91 (9.52)	10.28 (10.38)	8.87 (9.07)
[Ni(BBTuB)(ClO ₄) ₂]	Light green	2.615	8.28 (8.48)	9.12 (9.24)	7.88 (8.09)

broad assymmetric ligand field band in the region 13,000-17,000 cm^{-1} whose maxima lie at 15000 cm^{-1} corresponding to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition in a nearly octahedral arrangement. A charge-transfer band also appears at $\sim 27,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Co(II) complexes show an intense band in the region 16,000-17,000 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition in an approximately octahedral field. Ni(II) complexes resolve three bands at about 11,000, 14,000 and 27,000 cm^{-1} . In an octahedral approximation these bands can be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively. Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes possess low magnetic moments. The lower values may be attributed to antiferromagnetic interaction.

Based on the foregoing spectral features and magnetic moment values one of the probable structures (A or B) may be suggested for the complexes. The complexes are highly insoluble in water and common organic solvents. This seems to suggest a polymeric nature for the complexes (A) wherein each ligand molecule coordinates towards two metal ions in *trans* bi-bidentate form involving sulphur and oxygen atoms.

Fungicidal activity : The antifungal activity of the ligand and its metal complexes was assayed by the method of Horsfall¹⁴ using the agar plate technique. The percentage of inhibition was

TABLE 2—FUNGICIDAL SCREENING
AVERAGE PERCENTAGE INHIBITION AFTER 5 DAYS OF COLONY GROWTH AT 100 ppm., TEMP. = $31^\circ \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

Sl. No.	Compound	Organism		
		<i>A. niger</i>	<i>F. oxysporium</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
1.	BBTuB	51.5	53.8	33.6
2.	[Cu(BBTuB)Cl ₂]	92.5	76.9	55.2
3.	[Cu(BBTuB)Br ₂]	55.9	59.5	65.4
4.	[Cu(BBTuB)(NO ₃) ₂]	57.4	55.0	68.3
5.	[Cu(BBTuB)(ClO ₄) ₂]	52.3	62.9	58.6
6.	[Co(BBTuB)Cl ₂]	88.2	58.3	91.3
7.	[Co(BBTuB)Br ₂]	72.5	56.9	79.8
8.	[Co(BBTuB)(NO ₃) ₂]	28.6	42.9	25.7
9.	[Co(BBTuB)(ClO ₄) ₂]	25.9	33.8	29.5
10.	[Ni(BBTuB)Cl ₂]	56.4	57.0	51.9
11.	[Ni(BBTuB)Br ₂]	55.6	59.8	53.3
12.	[Ni(BBTuB)(NO ₃) ₂]	89.8	58.0	65.4
13.	[Ni(BBTuB)(ClO ₄) ₂]	75.2	65.6	78.5

calculated as reported earlier⁷. The fungicidal activity of various compounds is summarised in Table 2. The data reveal that all the complexes except compound nos. 8 and 9 are physiologically more active than the ligand. The reason may perhaps be due to the presence of C=O and C=S groups in the ligand as well as its complexes. This observation is more or less in accordance with the observation of Horsfall and coworkers^{1,5}. Hence all the compounds except nos. 8 and 9 may serve as antifungal agents against the organisms studied.

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